

MAQOM NAVLARI DOYRA USULLARINING SHAKLIY VA TARKIBIY MEZONLARI (FORMAL AND STRUCTURAL CRITERIA OF THE DOYRA USULS OF MAQOM VARIETIES)

Rasulov Marufjon

Associate Professor of the Department of Music, Faculty of Sports and Arts, Andijan State University

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Abstract. *The Uzbek maqom has historically gone through a great stage of development and formation. It has survived to our times as a cultural monument, without losing its invaluable value, if we may say so, under strong spiritual pressures. This article presents historical, analytical, and theoretical information on the characteristics of the Uzbek maqom varieties, their structure, the ideological expressive power of their categories, and the proportionality of their doyra usuls in their performances.*

Keywords: *Maqomat, Shashmaqom, Khorezm maqoms, Fergana-Tashkent maqom routes, Tasnif, Tarjei, Gardun, Mukhammas, Sakil, Doyra, Usullar.*

Annotatsiya. *O‘zbek maqomoti tarixan katta rivojlanish, shakllanish bosqichini bosib o‘tgan. Ta’bir joiz bo‘lsa kuchli ma’naviy bosimlar ostida o‘zining bebaxo qiymatini yo‘qotmasdan bizning davrlargacha madaniy yodgorlik sifatida yetib kelgan. Ushbu maqolada O‘zbek maqomoti navlarining o‘ziga xosliklari, tuzulishi, turkumlarining g‘oyaviy ifoda kuchi va ularning doyra usullari ijrolaridagi mutanosibliigi xususida tarixiy, taxliliy, nazariy ma’lumotlar keltirilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Maqomot, Shashmaqom, Xorazm maqomlari, Farg‘ona-Toshkent maqom yo‘llari, Tasnif, Tarjei, Gardun, Muxammas, Saqil, Doyra, Usullar.*

Introduction. Shashmaqom is the musical dictionary of the Uzbek people. It beautifully combines all the features of the highest genres of classical music. The composition of the harmonization of the principles of the usul is a direct manifestation of this process of proportional harmonization of the specific rhythmic structures of the components of the Muqoms, namely, usul, melody (tune), text (measures of the rhythm of the lyrics). We can say that Shashmaqom is a type of classical music that can fully and meaningfully express this proportion. Perhaps this is why the principles of the usul of Shashmaqom are distinguished from other genres by their comprehensive proportionality, orderliness, and perfection in content and essence.

Although the usuls have their own fundamental principles, it should be especially recognized that maqoms, in particular, in the formation of Shashmaqom, are guided by the unified order of the melody and text, which are related to the criterion of time. The factors that underpin the perfection and complexity of the usuls are their universality, versatility, tendency to artistic expression, and, of course, independence.

We have tried to explain that the usuls embody many aspects, the above-mentioned ideas, maqoms are melodic paths in the instrumental section, circle usuls are rhythmic formulas

adapted to express a certain image, to perform a certain rhythmic pattern. It is not surprising that this was actually taken into account during the formation of Shashmaqom usuls and served as the main criterion in the creation of usuls imbued with these qualities. After all, it is appropriate to say that each of these usuls is a specific formula that embodies individuality and many aspects. Ultimately, usuls are embodied as one of the factors determining the structural character of maqoms. Perhaps this is why all their aspects have been taken into account in the names of the usuls. Perhaps this is the reason why they were popularized based on these aspects. For example, it is no secret that the names of usuls such as Saqil, Hafif, Ramal or Muhammas, Charzarb, although they refer to a specific usul, are actually the names of the elements of the aruz system of literature, that is, poetry. It is worth noting that usuls - examples of classical music and, in particular, maqom art - have served to beautifully harmonize the possibilities of a specific composition and musical factors.

It is known that Shashmaqom consists of two large sections, namely Mushkilot and Nasr. Each of the sections is created based on a separate system of usuls. The usuls included in the mushkilot, that is, instrumental paths, of Shashmaqom are distinguished by their two aspects. At first glance, they can be called simple usuls. However, if we look directly at the composition of the melodies in the internal structural structures of the usuls and the logical form and execution of the formula in their proportional arrangement, we can certainly understand their second aspect, that is, their complexity. One of the reasons for this is that, first of all, these usuls are very close and similar to the formulas of the usuls given in ancient treatises. Therefore, there is reason to imagine that the system of usuls of the Shashmaqom instrumental section is directly imbued with spiritual and moral elements of religious foundations. Tasnif, Tarjei, Gardun, and especially Muhammas and Saqil - all of these names can be seen to contain a philosophical meaning and an entire concept.

The versatility of the usuls of the shashmaqom instrumental section is explained by the fact that they do not change in each type of maqom, but can serve as a basis for fully expressing the figurative features of the maqoms. If the Buzruk Classification expresses the aspects of the ug'ugvor, then in the Segoh Classification this usul preserves the times of the usul in reflecting the signs of the hijran of the spiritual state. It also provides characteristic performances of the original maqoms in the Rost, Navo, Dugoh and Iraq maqoms.

Let us try to interpret the foundations of the usul using the example of the Gardun usul: The circle usul reflects a specific circular movement in the celestial sphere. Therefore, it is said that the Gardun usul contains the image of the celestial sphere. Signs of uniqueness and infinity are felt in its movement, and its form can be imagined as follows:

Mukhammas actually means five. In music, it is precisely from the meaning of the phrase that 5 musical usuls are combined in muhammas. Of course, first of all, a 16-bar melodic core is formed by strictly adhering to the melodic structure and the processes of arranging themes in the form of a melody in order to reflect the content of the melody. Therefore, the composition criteria for the muhammas usul in embodying all aspects are very complex.

In muhammas, the five lines of the text are very beautifully and proportionately classified in the formation of the melody, the formation of the theme and its development, which is the basis for the comprehensive perfection of the work. All this is expressed in a 16-bar melodic structure. The sequential movement of 5 usuls based on melodies requires great skill. In addition, muhammas are a separate form in musical creativity, like poetry. It is a compositional practice that can even claim to be considered a separate direction in music creation. The most difficult and most important aspect of the melody is the connection between its successive parts and their harmony in tone, text, and style.

Summary:

- In short, the usuls included in the Shashmaqom composition have served as the basis for classical music performance and performance practice with their antiquity, perfection and complexity.

- Khorezm maqoms, Fergana-Tashkent maqom paths, as well as the criteria for the composition of instrumental works were created based on the formal, structural, and categorization rules of the Shashmaqom;

- Shashmaqom style patterns were used in accordance with the traditions of the oases;

- It is appropriate to recognize that the usuls of maqom types and their rules of organization, formal and structural criteria, performance traditions, all have common aspects;

- The usul systems of Khorezm maqoms do not differ from the usuls included in the Shashmaqom composition. The attractiveness of Khorezm usuls is embodied in their local aspects of their uniqueness. Local aspects are clearly reflected in the Khorezm interpretations of the Khorezm "ufors", "zarbul fath", "Suvoralari", and "Nasr" usuls;

- In the practice of creativity and performance of the Fergana-Tashkent maqom routes, the usul known as “Zarb ul-qadim” was the basis for the creation of many classical works. This usul is also considered a form of Sarakhbor. Therefore, most of the works on the Fergana-Tashkent routes, namely, works with native maqom characteristics such as Ushshaqlar, Dugoh, Segoh, Bayotlar, Hojiniyaz, Cho‘li Iroq, Chorgohlar, have been created and performed using this usul.

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